

A surreal scene featuring a man with a beard and a top hat standing over a woman lying on her back on the ground. The background consists of concentric, wavy lines on a textured surface, creating a hypnotic effect. The entire image is overlaid with a semi-transparent pink filter.

IN PURSUIT OF THE MARVELLOUS

SURREALISM, TONY SHIELS'S BIZARRE MAGICK,
AND THE PERFORMATIVE TURN

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RÉSUMÉ

À la croisée de l'histoire de l'art, des études magiques, de l'illusiographie et des théories de la performance, l'analyse de la trajectoire de Tony Shiels (1938–2024), de son apprentissage de la peinture surréaliste jusqu'à la fondation de la « magie bizarre », permet de mettre en lumière la manière dont le merveilleux se déploie transmédiatiquement et peut s'actualiser lors d'une performance. L'œuvre magique de Shiels offre un laboratoire pour comprendre le rôle méconnu joué par le surréalisme dans le tournant performatif, grâce à sa connexion avec l'anthropologie et l'éсотérisme, et à l'introduction dans l'art du XX^e siècle du merveilleux, de la magie, du mythe et du sacré. Cette impulsion décisive a conduit à l'émergence d'avant-gardes théâtrales et illusionnistes cherchant à renouer avec la dimension rituelle des performances. L'artiste anglais subversif Tony Shiels est le principal artisan de la réinvention des performances illusionnistes à la fin des années 1960. En les reconnectant à l'« occulture », il relance une dynamique de création artistique en prise avec la culture magique populaire. L'art de Shiels possède une dimension « mythopoiétique » (créatrice de mythes) qui réalise le programme surréaliste en étant capable de donner vie à des légendes locales par l'invocation de monstres. Le développement de cet art magique lié à la contreculture constitue un contrepoint essentiel pour comprendre le tournant performatif des années 1970.

ABSTRACT

At the crossroads of art history, magic studies, illusiography, and performance theory, the analysis of the trajectory of Tony Shiels (1938–2024), from his apprenticeship in surrealist painting to the founding of 'Bizarre Magick', sheds light on how the marvellous unfolds transmediatically and can be actualised during a performance. Shiels's magical work offers a laboratory for understanding the little-known role played by surrealism in the performative turn, thanks to its connection with anthropology and esotericism, and to the introduction into twentieth-century art of the marvellous, magic, myth, and the sacred. This pivotal impulse led to the emergence of theatrical and illusionist avant-gardes seeking to reconnect with the ritual dimension of performances. The subversive English artist Tony Shiels was the main architect of the reinvention of illusionist performances in the late 1960s. By reconnecting them to 'occulture', he revived a dynamic of artistic creation in touch with popular magical culture. Shiels's art has a 'mythopoeitic' (myth-making) dimension that fulfilled the surrealist agenda by being able to bring local legends to life through 'monster-raising'. The development of this counter-culture-related magical art is an essential counterpoint for understanding the performative turn of the 1970s.

KEYWORDS

magic, illusionism, surrealism, shamanism, popular culture

MOTS-CLÉS

magie, illusionnisme, surréalisme, chamanisme, culture populaire

Cover image: Tony 'Doc' Shiels levitating his daughter Kate, black and white photography by Lawrence Lawry, Gwenap Pit, Cornwall, January 1979. Courtesy of Lawrence Lawry.

INTRODUCTION

*In loving memory of Tony Shiels,
who sadly passed away on the very day this
article was finalised.
Nnidnid!*

Illusionism is a still little-known performance art. One of the goals of contemporary illusiography is to understand the complex relationships between illusionism and magic since the Middle Ages (During 2002; Rioult 2023a). After presenting themselves primarily as ‘professors of physics’ in the eighteenth century, illusionists took on the name of ‘prestidigitators’ in the nineteenth century, before the term ‘magicians’ came to the fore in the twentieth century. At the same time, however, to avoid being associated with spiritualist and psychic swindlers, the illusionist community rejected all forms of the occult (Tabet and Taillefer 2015). Cut off from its magical and occult sources, from the 1940s to the 1960s, illusionism increasingly *trivialised* magic (Burger and Neale 1995: 8). The observation of a profound *dissonance* between the concept of ‘magic’ in its entire cultural dimension and the reality of the spectacular practice it named (prestidigitation) was the starting point for a new form of illusionism: ‘Bizarre Magick’. At the end of the 1960s, some artists sought to *reclaim magic* and reconnect with its occult roots in order

to renew their approach to magical performances (Taylor and Nolan 2015; Goto-Jones 2016; Taylor 2018, 2020; Rioult 2023b) and more generally with the late 1960s and early 1970s ‘occulture’, defined as ‘a vast spectrum of beliefs and practices sourced by Eastern spirituality, Paganism, Spiritualism, [...] and a range of beliefs emanating out of the general cultural interest in the paranormal’ (Partridge 2004: 70). Since the 1970s, Bizarre Magick has established itself as an illusionist artistic paradigm in its own right. It is now supported by a large artistic movement, mainly anglophone, with several thousand enthusiast ‘bizarrists’ throughout the world.

Coinciding with the emergence of performance studies in the United States (Schechner 1966, 1970, 1973, 1977; Turner 1974, 1977) and sharing their main issues, the study of this tipping point sheds light on the performative turn of the 1970s from a new vantage point. While Bizarre Magick is generally considered a phenomenon specific to the anglophone counter-culture (Taylor and Nolan 2015: 10), a study of the vast and complex work of the English artist Tony Shiels (b. 1938), its principal founder, makes it possible to identify another decisive legacy, that of surrealism. As theatre scholar John Freeman points out, the question of performance should be reintegrated into the filiation of the avant-gardes, in particular futurism, Dadaism, and surrealism, and not only considered from the point of view of theatrical genealogy (Freeman 2007: 33–54). Likewise, performance scholar Pannill Camp has recently shown the debt that performance studies owes to the French school of sociology and anthropology, through Durkheim and his followers (Camp 2023; Smith and Alexander 2005: 9–11). Moreover, as I will show, surrealism and anthropology are deeply intertwined. This step backwards enables us to grasp the complex dynamic that gave rise to a new way of thinking about performance and to study its simultaneous deployment, from the late 1960s onwards, in performance studies on the one hand, and in Tony Shiels’s Bizarre Magick on the other.

In order to show the pivotal role of surrealism and how Tony Shiels fits into a wider performative framework that integrates artistic, anthropological, and occult influences, this essay adopts a transdisciplinary historical and analytical approach. By paying close attention to the intellectual genealogy of thinkers and artists, it combines archival research, references to primary documents, and an interpretive analysis of artistic movements.

The essay first shows how surrealism deployed the essential themes of performance studies and Bizarre Magick, highlighting its *mythopoietic* (myth-making) ambition. I then present Shiels's youth as a surrealist artist, trained in Paris in the 1950s, and analyse the key role he played in the birth of Bizarre Magick, providing the first history of the birth and structuring of this artistic movement. Finally, I look at how Shiels pushed Bizarre Magick to the limit by offering a true realisation of the surrealist programme through 'monster-raising', a new kind of performance.

ON THE TRAIL OF MAGICAL ART: SURREALISM, AN AESTHETIC OF WONDER JOINING ART AND ANTHROPOLOGY

Although the presence of illusionism (with the meaning of prestidigitation, conjuring trick, or sleight of hand) should not be overestimated in these movements, in 1920, during two Dadaist shows, Louis Aragon and Philippe Soupault performed prestidigitation tricks (Sanouillet 2016: 141, 150), in line with the Dadaist *aesthetics of shock* inherited from cinema (Benjamin [1939] 2006: 266–67). Indeed, in France, it was precisely illusionism that had formed the matrix of cinema through Georges Méliès (Tabet 2018). However, while Dada devoted itself to the systematic destruction of the 'aura' of its creations (Benjamin [1939] 2006: 266–67), surrealism sought to re-enchant the world by opening up to the powers of the unconscious, the imagination, the marvellous, and above all magic. Responding to the injunction of Guillaume Apollinaire (inventor of the term 'surrealism') to explore the possibilities of the 'depths of consciousness' proper to the 'time of magic' (Apollinaire [1918] 1980: 35–37), the first *Manifesto of Surrealism* (1924) set out to explain the 'secrets of surrealist magical art' (Breton 1972: 29).

Of course, there is no illusionism here but rather a desire to put the Western 'real world' on 'trial' (Breton 1972: 47) by resorting to forms of radical

otherness, such as magic or primitivism (Blachère 1996). Since the early twentieth century, modern art circles (Matisse, Picasso, Braque, Derain, et al.) have been fascinated by the aesthetics of African art (Laude 1968). Beyond this aesthetic dimension, during the inter-war period, surrealism brought about the first strong link between art and ethnography. The founding of the Institute of Ethnology, in 1925, occurred in a period of intense surrealist activity. Surrealists forged contacts and friendships with anthropologists and attended their courses (Debaene 2002). Similarly, during their exile in New York during the Second World War, anthropologist Claude Lévi-Strauss became friend with the surrealists (Max Ernst, André Breton, and Georges Duthuit), and they frequented together ethnographic art dealers (Lévi-Strauss 1983: 348). Although passionate about tribal art and ethnography, Breton was not a thinker of the sacred and its rituality, unlike Artaud, Caillois, and Bataille, who were very attracted to the surrealist movement before socially breaking with it.

In 1936, Antonin Artaud travelled to Mexico to discover the rites of the Tarahumara Indians (Artaud 1971). Just before leaving, the playwright launched the publication of *The Theatre and Its Double* by bringing together a collection of texts written between 1931 and 1936, which presents his alchemical conception of theatre, the rituality of Balinese theatre, and the magical and sorcerous nature of what he called ‘Oriental’ theatre. Magic is opposed to the ‘fossilised idea of theatre’ (Artaud 1938: 12). This work became one of the main references for the theatrical avant-garde of the 1960s, such as Jerzy Grotowski, Eugenio Barba, and Peter Brook. Through them, it contributed to establish the anthropological and ritual dimension of performance studies.

In 1937, a group of dissident surrealists (including Bataille and Caillois) founded the Collège de Sociologie to put the question of the sacred back at the centre of their concerns. In their initial programme, the founders stated that the aim was to build a ‘*sacred sociology*’ devoted to

‘the study of social existence in all those of its manifestations in which the active presence of the sacred comes to light’ (Ambrosino et al. 1937; my translation). This space for philosophical, ethnographic, and sociological research on the fringes of academic institutions served as a laboratory for the emergence of new subjects.

Shamanism was still a little-known subject at the time and played a key role in the discussions. Literary scholar Denis Hollier recalls that ‘the question of shamanism was at the heart of the Collège’s theme’ (Hollier [1979] 1995: 581; my translation). Russian-born Anatole Lewitzki — a member of the French Resistance, who was shot before he could complete his thesis on Siberian shamanism — presented his research to the Collège and provided French intellectuals access to the work of little-known Russian ethnographers (Lewitzki [1979] 1995). Caillois saw in shamanism the possibility of creating a synthesis between ‘religious powers and the domain of infernal forces’ (Hollier [1979] 1995: 582; my translation). As we shall see in detail later on (particularly in Shiels’s work), the shaman played a key role in the intellectual apparatus of the 1960s because he overcame all the oppositions between magic and religion, priest and actor, sorcerer and possessed, ritual and play, reality and illusion, and so on. He was an in-between figure, an intermediary, subverting the rigid categories of Western thought, as the ‘trickster’ popularised by Paul Radin (1956). It is worth pointing out that the thesis equating the function of the priest and the actor in the original figure of the shaman is the subject of vigorous debate in theatre studies. For example, it is defended by E. T. Kirby (1974, 1975) and opposed by Eli Rozik (2002: 89). Regardless of whether it has any historical basis — the question is not relevant to the present study — this thesis has had an important influence on artists associated with Bizarre Magick (Shiels 1989; Burger and Neale 1995; Chelman 1999: 181–93; Burger and McBride 2003). More generally, shamanism plays an important role in performance studies, linking ritual and theatre. Indeed,

for Schechner, ‘what shamans do indicates that the earliest human performances were both entertaining and sacred’ (2013: 199).

Anthropologist Franz Boas’s (1895) analysis of the use of illusionist techniques by Kwakiutl shamans provided food for a broader conception of the performative act. These accounts led Duthuit — a writer close to the surrealists — to think that ‘the value of a work [...] is linked to the ritual performance, which, being part theatre and part prestidigitation, creates the conditions for belief in the presence of supernatural entities’ (Duthuit [1946] 1974; Mauzé 2017: 198; my translation). Then, building on Boas’s reports, Lévi-Strauss analysed the links between shamanism and psychoanalysis, illusionism, and puppet shows in two fundamental articles (1949a, 1949b). He revived the Maussian intuition of the importance of ‘the moment of the conjuring trick (*moment de la prestidigitation*)’. Indeed, the illusionist performance is the only moment that enables the coincidence of the ‘two very intense individual states’ of the shaman and his patient (Mauss 1972: 123; Mauss and Hubert [1903] 1950; Crapanzano 2005). At the same time, religion scholar Mircea Eliade (1950) published his seminal work on shamanism, also highlighting the role of performances and wonder-working.

The works of the French ethnographic surrealist school — far beyond Artaud — were decisive in the emergence of avant-garde theatre. Barba reports that in the early 1960s, during his work sessions with Grotowski, ‘we moved on to alchemy, shamanism, trance, rituals, the *misterium tremendum et fascinans* [theorised by Rudolf Otto], and there reappeared the same nucleus of authors: Jung, Durkheim, Lévi-Bruhl, Mauss, Lévi-Strauss, Caillois, Bachelard, and Eliade’ (1999: 50). Through this contribution, the centre of gravity of the performing arts shifts from aesthetics to ‘mythico-ritual practice’ (Borie 1989: 214). Theatre regained its ritual dimension. This would soon become the central issue in the theoretical alliance between Victor Turner and Richard Schechner.

Beyond his involvement in the Collège de Sociologie, Caillois embodies a singular possibility of surrealism. In a letter written in 1934 (and made public in 1935), Caillois (1974) rejected Breton’s position based on the generalisation of irrationalism and the marvellous. On the contrary, he defended the ridge position of the fantastic, of which he was one of the main French thinkers (Bozzetto 1989). The rigorous exercise of reason conditions, by contrast, the irruption of the fantastic and its vertigo, leveraging the dialectic of the sacred and the profane. His general theory of play (including theatre and performance) is placed under the sign of the ritual and the sacred (Caillois 1946, 1958). Quickly translated into English (Caillois 1961), it influenced thinkers on play and ritual, in particular *In Praise of Play* (1969) by the pastor, magician, and ritual theorist Robert E. Neale. Neale is best known in the world of illusionism for having written one of the major theoretical books of the post-Bizarre Magick period (but totally influenced by it) in collaboration with Eugene Burger, *Magic and Meaning* (Burger and Neale 1995). Similarly, Turner (1986) and Schechner (2013: 93–94) would also make use of Caillois’s work, albeit in a rather limited way, reducing him to being only a thinker of typologies of play and consequently obscuring his relationship to the sacred, despite its centrality.

Occultism and magic are the final piece of the surrealist puzzle (Bauduin 2014; Subelytė et al. 2022). Although this occult dimension goes beyond the analysis of performance studies, it is nonetheless one of the major keys to understanding the post-war period, from the publication of *Arcane 17* (1945). While this theme was already present in their early texts in a rather diffuse way, it was consolidated among the surrealists by the 1950s through the publication of veritable treatises. Kurt Seligmann published his *History of Magic* (1948). Michel Carrouges, a spiritualist, ufologist, and science fiction writer, devoted a study to ‘Esotericism and Surrealism’ (1950: 19–85). Breton wrote *Magical Art* (1957) and presented magical art as what had survived ‘the disappearance of all constituted magic’ (Breton 2008: 53; my translation).

Although Breton does not mention illusionism, from the earliest surrealist works, the illusionist is a subliminal figure, as evidenced by the use of an engraving from *La Nature* (D^r Z... 1891), depicting the trick of the vanishing woman (invented by Buatier de Kolta) in Max Ernst's collage 'Rencontre de deux sourires' (Meeting Two Smiles). This reference intended for insiders was also preceded by a poetic wink to the 'prestidigitateur' (sleight-of-hand artist) (Ernst 1922: 9, 14). Likewise, for the Belgian surrealists Paul Nougé and René Magritte, the artist is a prestidigitator who knows how to manipulate reality (Fischer 2019: 183–93; Gillain 2020).

But overall, for the surrealists, the artist is a magician. Their 'role [...] consists in creating new myths' (Bauduin 2014: 145, 192). Magic is the operative part of myth, and myth is the condition of magic. Indeed, art historian Tessel Bauduin points out that 'for the Bretonian surrealists, magic hardly functioned without myth' (2014: 146). With the term 'magic', Breton highlights the fact that art affects the public, and can change the world, leveraging the magical dimension of the human mind. One expression of this way of thinking is the use of the monster figure in surrealist works (such as the androgyne, the sphinx, the Minotaur, or Melusina). For example, the archetypal figure of Melusina, a hybrid monster, part woman, part serpent, plays a pivotal role in *Arcane 17*, banding together 'myth, fairytales and heterodox thought [...] into one message of hope and regeneration' (Bauduin 2014: 157–58). As characterised by Antoine Faivre, the leading French scholar in esotericism, esoteric knowledge is experiential and transformative knowledge (2019: 16).

This taste for the occult also spread in circles close to the surrealists. Louis Pauwels, who was initially close to Breton and then Dalí, published his account of the method of Georges Gurdjieff (1954), an occultist turned towards the East, who had a profound influence on Grotowski

and Barba (Christof 2017). With the collaboration of Jacques Bergier, he also published in 1955 a French translation of *The Book of the Damned* (1919), a pre-surrealist collection of strange, marvellous, and unexplained facts compiled by Charles Fort. Pauwels and Bergier saw in this work a Dadaist and surrealist act in the field of science:

The Book of the Damned [...] was published in New York in 1919 and provoked a revolution in intellectual circles. Before the first manifestations of Dadaism and Surrealism, Charles Fort introduced into science what Tzara, Breton and their disciples were going to introduce into art and literature: a defiant refusal to play at a game where everybody cheats, a furious insistence that there is 'something else'.
(Pauwels and Bergier 1960: 160; 1964: 95)

The same year, in the same collection, the two authors also introduced H. P. Lovecraft to France, and through him their conception of 'fantastic realism' (Lovecraft 1955). Finally, the publication of *The Morning of the Magicians* in 1960, by establishing itself as a bestseller, marked a decisive stage in the democratisation of the major themes of the occult and the supernatural (Pauwels and Bergier 1960; Lagrange 2016). 'Fantastic realism' was a method that took over from surrealism (Pauwels and Bergier 1960: 474–75, 1964: 279). Through it, Pauwels and Bergier brought together contemporary science, history, parapsychology (extrasensory perception, PSI), fantastic literature (Lovecraft, Arthur Machen, Arthur C. Clarke), anthropology, esotericism, and spirituality. They made a powerful contribution to the 'renaissance of Western occultism' (Lagrange 2013). And, more broadly, particularly in the English-speaking world, the counter-culture of the 1960s mixed with occult themes (new age, Wicca, astrology, magic, UFOs, etc.) and gave rise to what the historian of religion Christopher Partridge calls the 'occulture' (2004: 70), as already mentioned and briefly described in the introduction.

D^r Z... 1891. 'Physique amusante : La femme escamotée', *La Nature*, 19 no. 950: 176. Courtesy BnF/Gallica.

Max Ernst. 1922. *Les Malheurs des immortels* (Paris: Librairie Six), p. 14. Public domain (The Public Domain Review).

A study of the 1920–60 period shows that surrealism *lato sensu* was the site of a new articulation between art and anthropology, aimed at criticising the old Western art forms. In the field of illusionism, this complex dynamic was to continue in the work of Tony Shiels, but also in the academic field: it permeated performance studies.

SUBVERTING ART: THE YOUTH OF TONY SHIELS, SURREALIST ARTIST AND ONEIROMANCER

Although he is primarily known in illusionist circles as a central figure of the Bizarre Magick movement, Shiels is first and foremost a painter and performer whose work unfolds in multiple directions (Shiels and Madsen 1966; Chorvinsky 1991; Cousins 1995, 2017; White 2015). To understand the turning point of the 1970s, it is necessary to look back at his youth as a contemporary artist.

Born in 1938 in Salford, Anthony Shiels was subject to two distinct family artistic influences: modern art, on his mother's side and that of one of her cousins; magic, music, and performance on his father's and grandfather's side (White 2015: 11). His childhood was enchanted by the illusionist shows of Dante, The Great Lyle, and Luxor Gali Gali the Egyptian in Blackpool. The latter left him completely fascinated and awakened his passion for cups and balls. As a young teenager, he

presented his first shows to underprivileged children in Manchester and Liverpool. However, Shiels moved away from performing when he was about fifteen, as his love of art began to compete with his love of magic. Showing a predisposition for the fine arts, he entered Heatherley School of Fine Art in London, England's oldest independent art school, at the age of sixteen.

This separation from the world of illusionism lasted approximately ten years (Shiels and Madsen 1966). During this period, Shiels devoted himself to the visual arts. Seduced by modern art (in particular Picasso, Braque, Miró, Klee, etc.), he went to Paris in 1956, and then to Spain, to follow in the footsteps of these avant-garde painters. His paintings from this period were still strongly inspired by cubism. But his style soon freed itself from the rigidity of the cubist line. From now on, bodies in action would emerge from a dynamic interlacing of black lines delimiting areas of colour. It was also in Paris that he became acquainted with the work of Charles Fort (Shiels 1990: 38), probably in the collection 'Lumière interdite', published in November 1955, a few months before his arrival (Fort 1955). It is also likely that it was during this stay that he was initiated to surrealism.

In 1958, having recently married and become a father, Shiels moved to the Cornish seaside resort of St Ives. At the time, St Ives was one of the hotbeds of the English avant-garde, where surrealist art and occultism met, as they did in French artistic circles (Bracewell 2009). The painter, writer, and occultist Ithell Colquhoun epitomised this synthesis. However, unlike urban and Parisian surrealism, English artists had stronger links with the folklore and rurality inherent in Cornwall. Around the time of Shiels's arrival, Colquhoun and Sven Berlin, two influential artists of the Cornish avant-garde, were publishing works that portrayed the dark forces that haunt this land (Colquhoun 1957; Berlin 1962). A great fan of M. R. James and Arthur Machen, Shiels also drew

on this dimension of folk horror, which anchors the fantastic in rural witchcraft, legends, and surviving pagan rituals (Shiels 1975). In the family environment of his childhood, women told fortunes and practised spiritualism (White 2015: 42). Meanwhile, it was precisely this English countryside that was giving birth to Wicca (neo-pagan witchcraft) through the work of G. B. Gardner (1959, 1960), by bringing together the work of Margaret Murray (1921, [1931]) and forms of ritual and esoteric theatre (Lingan 2014). Wicca rapidly established itself in the 1960s as a new world religion and would have a lasting influence on the Bizarre Magick of the 1970s and 1980s, particularly through the involvement of the American illusionist and Wicca practitioner Tony An-druzzi (Adler 1979; Magus 2011).

In St Ives, Shiels focused his pictorial work on the thematic elements of his new environment (sea, beach, etc.). Following his principle of ‘crypto-figuration’ (Cousins 2017: 42), he liked to conceal the figurative behind the abstract, in order to force the viewer to make an interpretation. St Ives was thus a breeding ground for provocative young artists. Looking back on those years, Shiels explains: ‘I wanted to be genuinely subversive’ (White 2015: 28). Although he had always warmly recommended the study of Colquhoun’s work (Shiels 1989: 91), which was meticulous and ethereal, Shiels broke with the style of the artists of the previous generation (Colquhoun, Dalí). He rejected refined, intellectualised hermeticism, opting instead to be more brutal, provocative, and playful. The mountebank and the showman were back! Indeed, eyewitness accounts show that he developed surrealist exhibitions designed to shock: collages of seaweed or raw meat (‘The pleasures of the flesh’), the burning of a piano and a harmonium filled with souvenirs of the First World War, a Dadaist exhibition with an axe at the entrance so that the works could be destroyed if desired, and so forth (White 2015: 19–38). Art mixed with life. Performance was an extension of visual arts.

Tony Shiels, [*Sea head*], 19 May 1998, painting on beer mat, 92 × 92 mm. Collection Rioult.

Tony Shiels painting, photography, 2000s (?). Courtesy of the Shiels family.

Shiels left St Ives in 1963 but never gave up painting. Visual arts have accompanied him throughout his life and remained for him the most important of his artistic activities (Shiels 1991). Shiels has constantly defended the importance of the contribution made by surrealist artists and painters, who were capable of predicting the future, inventing forms, and making dreams come true. He emphasised this position in *The Cantrip Codex*, a manual for illusionists in which he explained his work:

Many early surrealists — people such as André Breton, Marcel Duchamp, Max Ernst, Ithell Colquhoun, Leonora Carrington, Salvador Dalí, Luis Buñuel, René Magritte, Man Ray, Victor Brauner, and others — could have been, and often were, superbly entertaining professional oneiromancers [who practice divination by the interpretation of dreams]. Cantrip-casters [that is, illusionists] will learn far more of real value, from a study of surrealism, than from a hundred lessons in legerdemain. (Shiels 1989: 91)

Thus, there is no clear separation between performance and painting, as magical forms have a transmedial existence. For example, for Shiels, Dalí's melting clocks¹ are a prefiguration, even an influence, of Uri Geller's spoon bending (Shiels 1989: 89–90).

1. Salvador Dalí, *The Persistence of Memory*, Portlligat (?), 1931, oil on canvas, 24 × 33 cm (New York, MOMA, inv. 162.1934).

RECONNECTING WITH MAGIC: THE BIRTH AND STRUCTURING OF BIZARRE MAGICK

In the mid-1960s, although he had never really stopped practising, Shiels turned his attention back to the world of illusionism and made a name for himself by sending notable contributions to leading magic magazines such as *The Budget*, *The New Jinx*, *The Linking Ring*, and *The Gen*. As Eugene Burger (1986) analyses, at this time, illusionism in the UK was at a low ebb, suffering from a lack of creativity. Thus, English illusionism was moving away from all magic and all fantastic, precisely at the time when fantastic cinema was in full swing. Between 1958 and 1974, Hammer Film Productions (London) produced no fewer than nine films in its *Dracula* saga (with more made by other production companies). It was against this backdrop of a deep disconnect between popular culture and the illusionist scene that the Scotsman Charles Cameron and the Englishman Tony Shiels broke with traditional illusionism.

More generally, the tension that gave rise to Bizarre Magick was not new, and also bore the legacy of the questions raised by mentalism and 'mental magic' in the mid-twentieth century, emblematically represented by the magazine *The Jinx* (1934–41) compiled by Theo Annemann (1907–42), which would remain one of the points of reference for Bizarre Magick (Cameron 1967a). The generational dimension seems particularly important. The great mentalism stars of the previous generation were beginning to fade (Joseph Dunninger, 1892–1975, Maurice

Jack Fogel, 1911–81, Chan Canasta, 1920–99, among others). The new generation, born in the 1930s, sought to succeed them and make their mark: Charles W. Cameron (1927–2001), Bob Lynn / Tony Raven (1930–2005), Kreskin (1935–2024), Roy Fromer (1937–91), T. A. Waters (1938–98), Tony Shiels (1938–2024), Eugene Burger (1939–2017), Uri Geller (b. 1946), Phil Goldstein / Max Maven (1950–2022).

In my view, the real impetus came from Shiels in 1966. In his two seminal articles ‘Puzzlers or Paranormalists?’ (1966a) and ‘Jabberwocky’ on telling ghost stories (1966b) for *The Budget*, Shiels unwittingly signed the birth certificate of Bizarre Magick. In them, he tackled a thorny question inherited from mentalism: ‘Should performers of mental magic claim to possess genuine psychic powers?’ (Shiels 1966a: 20). The answer was given by the *Zeitgeist*, manifested in the success of contemporary film and television productions. Shiels mentioned the following films and series: *7 Faces of Dr Lao* (US film, 1964), *Night of the Demon* (UK film, 1957), *The Addams Family* (US TV series, 1964), and *Out of This World* (UK TV series, 1962). Shiels swapped the elitist, esoteric culture of the surrealist artists — without abandoning their essential aim of re-enchanting the world — for more popular and accessible forms of occultism.

As he sought to connect with his audience, Shiels recommended drawing on pop culture, and in particular the emerging fantastic film industry. It was a question of meeting a real expectation: ‘The public WANTS to believe in the unbelievable. [...] The public wants to believe, wants to be amazed, astounded and even terrified’ (Shiels 1966a: 20). In broad strokes, Shiels sketched out one of the first maps of the central themes of future (bizarre) magick, where the addition of the final ‘K’ is a nod to the English occultist Aleister Crowley. This occultist and practitioner of black ‘magick’ had a major influence on anglophone counter-culture. He is featured on the cover of one of the world’s

best-selling albums: *Sergeant Pepper’s Lonely Hearts Club Band* by the Beatles, released in 1967. Following the structural dichotomy present in the title of his article ‘Puzzlers or Paranormalists?’, Shiels contrasts the illusionists who confine themselves to presenting puzzles (‘puzzlers’) with those who confront the public’s attraction to the supernatural (‘paranormalists’):

Why is there such continued popular interest in witchcraft, E.S.P., poltergeists, clairvoyance and magick (with a K.)? Because everyone has a taste for the unusual and thrilling which is not catered for by a series of amusing parlour puzzles. (Shiels 1966a: 21)

This short seminal article condenses many of the motifs that would become the hallmarks of Bizarre Magick: supernatural themes; rejection of the aesthetic form of traditional prestidigitation; the opposition between puzzler and magician; the primacy of the emotion felt by the spectator, particularly fear; references to the occult and the fantastic specific to the counter-culture; recourse to external media (literature, cinema, and television) to nourish the aesthetic of the illusionist performing art.

An article by Shiels in *The New Jinx* a few months later also shows that what was at stake was the *cultural reappropriation* of the magical tradition by illusionism:

Agrippa, Roger Bacon, Cagliostro, Doctor Dee, Eliphas Levi, Albertus Magnus, Nostradamus, Papus and Sedir. [...] Do some reading about these magicians so you can make your patter sound authentic. (Shiels 1966c)

However, this new way of performing was not without shock in illusionist circles:

I started to put my mind to working out plot as if I was writing a story, telling a tale, and black magic came into it. I started writing a few things for magicians' magazines that involved plots and this dreadful subversive thing — pretending that it was real magic and that you were working with the dark power of the occult — that was regarded as sinful by a number of the straight magicians.

(Shiels 2005; White 2015: 46)

A short selection of tricks from his first booklet *Thirteen!* ([1967] 1977) gives a good idea of the illusionist performances Shiels staged: a mandrake root placed in a sealed 'alchemical' vase comes to life when the magician whispers a magic formula, thus becoming a 'homunculus'; the power of the images of a Marseille tarot — the 'devil's picture book' — is used as a basis for a mind-reading experiment; the burning of a strange liquid plunges the audience into a gloomy darkness, where two cats' eyes suddenly appear; finally the storytelling of the ghost story 'Whistle, and I'll come' (M. R. James) sets the mood for the appearance of an old whistle, followed by that of a ghost in the darkness. The book — 'the best in offbeat magic we've seen in a long time' — was an immediate success (Jones 1967: 445). Moreover, twenty years later, it was considered 'still good after all these years' by the official journal of the Society of American Magicians ([Goodsell] 1987).

The approach is the same for the Scottish illusionist Charles Wesley Cameron, who recommends introducing his 'Voodoo Flames' routine by explaining:

Black magic, states the mentalist, is on the increase. He tells his audience that he has studied this strange subject for many years and offers to show them just what a Black Magician can do using his strange Satanic powers. (Cameron 1967b: 6)

Slowly but surely, the late 1960s saw the emergence of the first corpus of autonomous publications on which the Bizarre Magick movement was to be based. These small and summary pamphlets were produced by Shiels and Cameron. Shiels published *Thirteen!* ([1967] 1977), *Something Strange* ([1968]), and *Daemons, Darklings and Doppelgangers* ([1969] 1981). Cameron published *Witches' Brew* ([1967c] 1978), the magazine *The Cauldron* (1967–68, ten issues), and the *Handbook of Horror* (1969). At the time, the notion of Bizarre Magick was not yet in use. Cameron generally spoke of 'weird magic' (Cameron [1967] 1978: 35; 1969: 43). It is hard not to see in this term a reference to the famous American magazine *Weird Tales* (1923–54), which published Lovecraft among others, and which enchanted the adolescence of these magicians.

This phase of development culminated in Tony Raven's launch of *Invocation* (July 1974), a magazine explicitly devoted — according to its subtitle — to 'Weird and Bizarre Magick'. The first issue was under the patronage of Cameron, who wrote the opening and agenda-setting article of the magazine. His article 'Magic ... or Magick!' opens with the following *incipit*: 'The "average" magician has long since given up dread — what he requires is a sound Gothic revival! [...] Fortunately, those who practice this strange art are not "average" magicians' (Cameron 1974). Already in this first issue, the publisher announced forthcoming contributions by Shiels, which would lead to an entire special issue devoted to him in July 1975 (No. 5). Until the 1990s, the magazine was to become a meeting point for artists all committed to this path (such as Tony Andruzzi, Stephen Minch, and Eugene Burger). By federating their work and thoughts, *Invocation* has turned Bizarre Magick into a veritable artistic movement, rapidly establishing itself as its backbone. It covers all the major themes of Western occult culture, from Wiccan rituals to shamanism to supernatural horror literature. But, more generally, *Invocation* bears witness to the emergence and appeal of a new form of illusionist performance art, emancipated from traditional

Tony 'Doc' Shiels performing linking rings, black and white photography by Lawrence Lawry, Gwenap Pit, Cornwall, January 1979. Courtesy of Lawrence Lawry.

frameworks and determined to dissolve the boundary between reality and fiction.

Strikingly, this period corresponds to the development phase of performance studies (Schechner 1977). Against a backdrop of ethnography, Schechner explains how performance art blends several arts together and dissolves the opposition between dream and reality, performer and spectator, freeing itself from mimetic theatre (1970: 130–32). Similarly, 1974 was also the year in which *The Drama Review (TDR)* published its special ‘Popular Entertainments’ issue, which included two articles dealing with illusionism: ‘The Actor and the Magician’, by playwright Julian M. Olf (1974), and ‘The Shamanistic Origins of Popular Entertainments’, by E.-T. Kirby (1974), which was extended by *Ur-Drama* the following year (Kirby 1975).

Despite this *TDR* issue and strong thematic proximity, illusionism remained marginal in the field of performance studies. It remains in their official textbook only through a reference to Kirby (Schechner 2013: 199), and this despite Schechner having approached — through Lévi-Strauss — the question of illusionism in ritual contexts (Schechner 1973: 182, 1985: 121) and having supported the publication of *Performing Magic on the Western Stage* (Coppa, Hass, and Peck 2008: 2).

The opportunity was missed, probably because the avant-garde illusionists of the 1970s were then more committed to the renewal of their actual practice than to its written theorisation (which Shiels later did to serve as an activity report, in the late 1980s). In the same way, Kirby’s analysis, combined with Alfred Irving Hallowell’s (1971) study of the use of ritual conjuring among Canadian Indigenous people, belatedly fed into the thinking of illusionist theorist Eugene Burger (Burger and Neale 1995), recognised by *Magic Magazine* as one of the ‘100 [magicians] who shaped the art in America’ (Allen 1999: 56). Thus, for *TDR*,

illusionism was integrated into the field of popular spectacle and entertainment, which extended beyond the classical stage device and into other spaces and venues (McNamara 1974). The aim of these performances is to turn strollers into spectators, by attracting them with spectacular effects. It is a case of bringing the show to the audience, not waiting for them to come. Bizarre Magick, like performance art, breaks with the notions of a separate spectacular space and the fourth wall.

Shiels was working to dissolve the spectacular heterotopia, claiming in the purest surrealist tradition that he ‘believe[s] that — in magic, in art, and life generally — we should be constantly in pursuit of the “marvellous”’ (1989: 16). Far from the New York avant-gardes, Cornwall was witnessing the radicalisation of illusionism and the emergence of a new shamanic performance art: the hunt for unknown beasts and ‘monster-raising’.

RE-ENCHANTING THE WORLD: 'DOC' SHIELS, CHARLATAN, SHAMAN, AND MONSTER HUNTER

In 1970, in Cornwall, Shiels put on a 'tent show', a short performance under a big top, which his small troupe performed at fairs. Wearing a tall hat that made him instantly recognisable he played a mountebank nicknamed 'Doc', like the charlatans in westerns (White 2015: 57). Accompanied by his family and 'Prof' Vernon Rose, he mixed cups and balls, Chinese rings, great illusions, mentalism, sideshows, as well as puppetry and music. The time was ripe for popular shows, with the idea that real magic is hidden behind fairground illusionism. At first, Shiels began his show by emphatically declaring 'I am an absolute fake!' in order to disarm sceptics and leave believers free to consider this statement as an ironic precaution (Shiels 1974: 14).

However, he soon abandoned this position. In his 'Shamanifesto' (Shiels 1989: 11–29) — ironically placed under an epigraph by the Dadaist Jacques Rigaut, 'Watch out, I'm going to lie' (Rigaut 1970: 88) — Shiels declares: 'I hate disclaimers, and most audiences hate them too. To tell people that your bizarre miracles are "simply tricks" is to be condescendingly insulting and downright disappointing' (Shiels 1989: 14). This is why Shiels also refuses to use the trivial signifiers 'magician' and 'mentalist', preferring instead the mysterious, provocative title of 'cantrip-casting shamanic surrealchemist' (ibid.: 12). For Shiels, like the shamanic act, illusionist performance creates a space that makes real magic possible:

Tony 'Doc' Shiels performing the linking rings, colour photography by Lawrence Lawry, Gwenap Pit, Cornwall, January 1979. Courtesy of the Shiels family and Lawrence Lawry.

Tony 'Doc' Shiels, Gareth Shiels, Ewan Shiels, Vernon Rose (from left to right), photography, 1970s. Courtesy of the Shiels family.

Performing, writing, and thinking about trickery, illusion, legerdemain, hocus-pocus, and all such stuff, actually seems to make the genuine thing happen. [...] To perform a 'trick' is, in effect, to act out a piece of sympathetic magic, a homeopathic hex. (Shiels 1989: 48)

In this way, Shiels offers magicians a way of simultaneously assuming (tricked) illusionism and (real) magic.

In 1973, Uri Geller shook up the news and challenged scientists with his metal-bending feats, rapidly becoming a worldwide star. With the claim of genuine paranormal powers, Geller's performances sparked controversy in illusionist circles. Shiels (1973) goes against the *doxa*: illusionists should not reveal Geller's techniques and expose his frauds, but instead turn controversy into artistic opportunity. Analysing Geller's success and the violent rejection he received from illusionists, Shiels comes to a puzzling conclusion: 'Today's magicians are scared at the idea of real magic' (1974: 9). Bizarre Magick is one of the main responses to the paradoxical observation that magic has become anti-magic.

Geller shows magicians how to use the media. For Shiels, this is a revelation. Indeed, 'surprisingly few magicians know how to use, and to work with the news media' (1989: 83). Analysing the mechanics that had contributed to Geller's worldwide success, Shiels published the highly important *The Shiels Effect: How to Become a Psychic Superstar* (1976). In this book, he sets out to invent the next star of the occult from scratch. He describes in detail how a young, modern witch named Psyche could become a star leveraging the media, thanks to her acting skills, her knowledge of the occult, but also her knowledge of Bizarre Magick and mentalism. Of Scottish descent, she would use her powers to summon the Loch Ness monster and 'even has a photograph as "proof" of this. A photograph? Gosh!!!' (ibid.: 43).

'Up for the Jubilee Nessie!', *Daily Mirror*, 9 June 1977. Collection Riout.

Tom Fool's Theatre performing at Covent Garden (London), colour photography, ca. 1975. Courtesy of the Shiels family.

These speculations on how to become a star could be smiled at and dismissed as mere literary ramblings if Shiels had not put them into practice. Indeed, the Cornish local press was full of strange news. On 5 March 1976, the *Falmouth Packet* published two photos of an aquatic monster, the Morgawr, sent by a certain Mary F., who wished to remain anonymous. The newspaper received many letters. Shiels invited Michael McCormick, a monster hunter, and arranged an interview with the BBC. On 23 April the newspaper announced that a few naked witches would be ‘joining in the hunt’ (White 2015: 92). The *News of the World* and *Reveille* tabloids, always on the lookout for a scoop, published photos of Shiels, a naked witch (Psyche), and above

all the Morgawr, a few days later. A small brochure was also published to anchor and support the legend (Mawnan-Peller [Shiels?] 1976). This was a true transmedial apparatus combining performance (invocations, Wiccan rituals), photographs, sketches, and writing, using the media as an amplifier.

In the 1950s and 1960s, cryptozoology became an important part of the counter-culture, responding to the general public's taste for the unknown (Heuvelmans 1958, 1968). For several years, Shiels was the driving force behind several other cases of cryptozoology, such as the Owlman of Mawnan seen by children (1976–78), photos of fairies in 1976, and a photo of ‘Nessie’ in 1977 (Bord and Bord 1980; Chorvinsky 1991, 1992; Downes 2006). Following Shakespeare's dictum that ‘all the world's a stage’, Shiels is not only inspired by the ‘occulture’ but *produces it* himself. Playing with myths and media, Shiels sets up a veritable *mythopoiesis* that brings the dreams and latent images of English folklore into reality. I use ‘*mythopoiesis*’ (not ‘*mythopoesis*’) to mean that there is *poiesis* (ποίησις), defined as the production from the potentialities of a situation. Of course, in this case, this production is also poetic. Unknown before Shiels, the Morgawr now has its own Wikipedia page in six languages (‘Morgawr’ 2024). By sending photos of the Morgawr and Nessie to local and national newspapers, Shiels has probably contributed greatly to the general public's interest in cryptozoology. As is often the case, Bizarre Magick tends to merge with life itself and does not suffer from being reduced to mere stage time; on the contrary, it overflows it on all sides.

So as not to trivialise this performative practice, Shiels abandoned monster-raising and reverted to spectacular theatrical forms, which may be more traditional but are still fully subversive. So much so that *The Sun* newspaper (April 1978) devoted a full page to Shiels's family headlined ‘The Weirdest Family in the Land!’ (White 2015: 114). However, he

also continued to contribute to the *Fortean Times*. In 1982, much to the regret of Cornwall, which had lost its entertainer, he moved permanently to Ireland.

For Shiels, the end of the 1980s was a time to take stock, through an intense production of books. He first published *Nnidnid: Surreality* (1986), a confidential magazine devoted to surrealism. He then assessed his work as an illusionist with two books for magicians, in which he returned to Bizarre Magick and extended his earlier analyses: *Bizarre: The Surreal Sorcery of Tony 'Doc' Shiels* (1988) and *The Cantrip Codex: A Guide for the Advanced Enigmatist* (1989). Finally, he wrote *Monstrum: A Wizard's Tale* (1990), a mass-market work for all cryptozoology enthusiasts. As his biographer Rupert White rightly points out, through these four books, Shiels forcefully mobilises surrealism as a unitary artistic paradigm to account for his rich and tortuous career, and his multiple performance modalities (White 2015: 130). Ultimately, surrealism above all allows Shiels to break away from any rationalising temptation: 'Surrealists seek the marvellous in art and life. No explanation, nor any justification, is required' (ibid.: 154). In the mysterious interplay of correspondences and interpretations, everything is always open to the emergence of the unknown. Dreams are just waiting to take shape.

Tony Shiels (ed.), 1986. *Nnidnid: Surreality. Number One* →
(Ponsanooth: [Shiels]), black and white print enhanced with felt pen, with the addition
of a photo montage stuck to the back, copy no. 15/50.
Ex-collection of surrealist poet Rikki Ducornet (b. 1943); collection Rioult.

CONCLUSION

From that of avant-garde painter to that of monster-raising shaman, Shiels's polymorphous work sheds light on the background to the performative turn of the 1970s. Surrealism invented a new paradigm, between art and anthropology, against a backdrop of shock aesthetics, the sacred, magic, and the fantastic. Bizarre Magick and performance studies continued this impulse, each in their own way. Shiels, like Barba, explored the performative possibilities offered by surrealism and shamanism. The time was ripe for subversion, whether of illusionism or traditional theatre. However, where the avant-garde of the 1970s drew on Eastern theatre to re-enchant their performances (Barba, Brook), Shiels chose to invest English folklore (witchcraft, monsters) and performance venues far removed from any institution (fairs, countryside, bays). Closely linked to the emergence of the 'occulture', Shiels's mythopoietic work creates performance spaces where audiences can experience the shock of the marvellous and the thrill of magic. The performances form a complex whole that is not limited to stage representation. His use of the media proposes a radical form of 'showing doing', from the use of illusionist magazines where he disseminated his subversive approach to his peers, to the tabloid newspapers where he offered the general public the experience of the unknown. Hybridising arts and influences, Shiels proposed a new transmedial approach to magic.

The study of surrealist dynamics sheds new light on the performative revival of the twentieth century. It allows us to recreate the conditions of the fertile encounter between illusionism and performance studies, in the very place of the tearing of reality from which dreams emerge. •

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